

Jellyfish galaxies in clusters: the circumgalactic contribution to the cold gas in the stripped tails

Ritali Ghosh ¹

¹Joint Astronomy Programme, Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore 560012, India

²Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics, Garching 85748, Germany

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ABSTRACT

We carry out 3D-hydrodynamic simulations of a well-resolved interstellar disk and circumgalactic medium of a satellite galaxy moving through the intracluster medium (ICM) with radiative cooling. We explore the survival and contribution of CGM to the cold gas in the ram pressure-stripped tails at various inclinations of the normal to the disk plane to the wind. We quantify the origin of cold gas in the stripped tails by calculating the fraction of the passive scalars in that region. Initially, the origin of cold gas in the wake of a jellyfish galaxy, like JO201, can be attributed equally to the ISM and the CGM. However, as time progresses, a significant fraction of cold gas originates from condensation of the ICM gas. The inclusion of radiative cooling does not affect the CGM stripping timescale and is still dependent the CGM to ICM density contrast χ . As expected, the cold mass in the ISM differs from the hydrodynamic runs, as regions of the ISM where the restoring force is large enough to prevent stripping, are preserved for a long time.

Key words: galaxies: haloes – galaxies: clusters: intracluster medium – galaxies: evolution – galaxies: groups: general – methods: numerical

1 INTRODUCTION

While moving through the intracluster medium (ICM hereafter), hydrodynamic interactions with the hot ICM can create a disturbed gaseous distribution in the wake of the galaxy’s orbital path. Spectacular tails of *jellyfish galaxies*, which are satellite galaxies with distinct head-tail morphologies, reveal the hydrodynamic interaction going on between the gas stripped from the disk and the hot ambient ICM. Specifically, the moving galaxy experiences ram pressure from the surrounding ICM that strips off its gaseous components (Gunn & Gott 1972) without perturbing the stellar distribution. This can result in long tails of ionized gas trailing behind.

The observed tails are multiphase - the ionized (H α : Fumagalli et al. 2014; Poggianti et al. 2019; UV: Smith et al. 2010; Gullieuszik et al. 2023; George et al. 2023; X-ray: Sun et al. 2010), the neutral (HI: Cayatte et al. 1994; Poggianti et al. 2016), and even the molecular (CO: Jáchym et al. 2019; Moretti et al. 2023) phases co-exist (see Sun et al. 2022 and references therein). Ram pressure stripping (RPS hereafter) is the most plausible generic mechanism to remove the galaxy’s cold gas reservoir and quench it as it moves through the ICM.

Simulations often consider the direct interaction of the dense interstellar medium (ISM) with the hot ICM (Tonnesen & Bryan 2010; Choi et al. 2022; Roediger & Brüggén 2006, 2007; Jáchym et al. 2009; Tonnesen & Bryan 2021; Lee et al. 2022). These works

have been able to successfully explain some of the observed signatures like the truncation radius of jellyfish galaxies (radius where gravitational restoring pressure of the galaxy equals the ram pressure - the classic Gunn & Gott 1972 criterion). Stripping of the ISM is attributed to the disk’s density structure. The diffuse ISM can therefore be stripped easily compared to the dense molecular clouds (Kenney & Young 1989; Fumagalli et al. 2009; Abramson & Kenney 2014; Moretti et al. 2020; Bacchini et al. 2023).

Given the vast range of scales involved in the problem, a focus on the ISM-ICM interaction is a reasonable choice. However, we have shown in our earlier work (Ghosh et al. 2024) that the CGM, especially around massive satellites, can survive for a long time while orbiting through cluster outskirts. The diffuse CGM contains the majority of baryons associated with the host halo of the galaxy (Tumlinson et al. 2017, Bregman et al. 2018), brings in pristine gas from the intergalactic medium (IGM henceforth) and feeds and recycles material to and from the galactic disk. Losing such a huge reservoir would result in a restrained supply of fuel for star formation over cosmological timescales. Complete stripping of the CGM can lead to *strangulation*, whereby the galaxy quenches as the supply of cold gas to the disk is removed (Larson et al. 1980; Woo et al. 2015). ISM+CGM stripping is also crucial in explaining the ionized gas observed in the Magellanic stream (between the Large and Small Magellanic clouds) undergoing RPS in the Milky Way. Recently, Sparre et al. 2024 also explored the circumgalactic origin of cold gas in the stripped tail of their model galaxy. Understanding the co-evolution of ISM and CGM in RPS can therefore shed light on

* E-mail: ritalighosh@iisc.ac.in

Figure 1. The origin of cold gas in ram pressure stripping of the ISM and CGM of a galaxy by an ICM wind at 60° inclination with the number density of 10^{-3} cm^{-3} and velocity 1600 km s^{-1} . *From left:* The first panel shows the slice plot of number density in a zoomed region near the $(30 \times 50) \text{ kpc}$ region centered at the disk at $\sim 500 \text{ Myr}$. The second, third, and fourth panels show tracer from the disk, the CGM, and the ICM, respectively. The dense stripped gas (white regions in the leftmost panel) has a significant contribution from the CGM surrounding the galaxy (central panel).

galaxy quenching mechanisms as well as the nature of stripped tails in both cluster and group environments.

In this paper, we carry out a systematic study of the RPS of a galaxy, with mass and size comparable to the jellyfish galaxy JO201, as it faces a constant ram pressure from the ICM wind in presence of radiative cooling. We carry out 3D hydrodynamical simulations of RPS (without radiative cooling) in the rest frame of the galaxy. Our idealized simulations resemble a ‘wind-tunnel’ setup in which the ICM wind properties are imposed all over the domain beyond the virial radius of the galaxy. Within the virial radius, we include both the ISM and the CGM.

2 SIMULATION SETUP

Our simulations are carried out using PLUTO (v4.4p2), a conservative hydrodynamic code with static grid, developed by Mignone et al. 2007. The RPS simulations are performed in 3D-computational domain in Polar (R, ϕ, z) coordinates extends in the radial direction from $R_{\text{beg}} = 0.1 \text{ kpc}^1$ to $R_{\text{end}} = 240 \text{ kpc}$ and in the vertical direction for 480 kpc . All the simulations have a resolution of $(N_R \times N_\phi \times N_z) \equiv (820 \times 50 \times 640)$ with the disk resolved by 50 pc (the smallest grid size in our simulation). We use the HLLC (Harten, Lax, van Leer Contact) solver, with RK2 time-stepping and a linear reconstruction scheme, with a CFL number of 0.3.

Our model galaxy is initialized at the center of the simulation domain and the wind is directed along the \hat{z} -direction, with density ρ_{ICM} and v_{wind} . Table 1, lists the various runs performed at varying strengths of ram pressure P_{ram} , with the naming convention, followed in Ghosh et al. 2024, i.e., simulations are labeled as (PG/OG) $(n_{\text{ICM}}[\text{cm}^{-3}]v_{\text{rel}}[\text{km s}^{-1}])$, depending on runs where

Table 1. Compilation of the parameter space explored in this work for ISM+CGM stripping of a massive satellite, each at an inclination angle of 0, 30, 45, and 60 degrees.

Simulation label	$P_{\text{ram}} (\text{dyn cm}^{-2})$	$T_{\text{ICM}} (K)$	χ^\S
PG2e-5v800	1.30×10^{-13}	10^7	6.0
PG2e-5v1600	5.22×10^{-13}	10^7	6.0
OG4e-4v400	6.52×10^{-13}	10^7	0.3
OG1e-3v1600	2.61×10^{-11}	10^7	0.12
OG1e-4v800	6.52×10^{-13}	10^7	1.2
OG5e-4v800	3.26×10^{-12}	10^7	0.24
OG1e-3v800 [†]	6.52×10^{-12}	10^7	0.12
OG1e-2v800	6.52×10^{-11}	10^7	0.012
OG5e-3v1600	1.30×10^{-10}	10^7	0.024
OG3e-3v3151	3.03×10^{-10}	10^7	0.04

[†] Fiducial parameters

[§] Ratio of the average CGM density ($1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to the ICM density

[‡] \times indicates that CGM survives until the end of simulation

there is pressure equilibrium with PG, or as OG if a pressure jump exists between the CGM and ICM at the virial radius of the galaxy, and n and v_{rel} are respectively the number density and relative velocity with the wind.

2.1 Tracing the evolution of gas phases

We mark the initial distribution of each phase in our simulation domain - the ISM (at $10^4 K$), the CGM (at $10^6 K$), and the $10^7 K$ hot ICM, with a passive scalar of 1 to represent the initial contribution, and 0 for its absence, in the presence of radiative cooling, the CGM in the vicinity of the cold disk can cool very fast and contribute to a slight enhancement in the cold mass. We, therefore,

¹ Note that $R = 0$ is outside the active simulation domain in Polar geometry as all cells, including the ghost cells, must have $R > 0$.

follow a relabelling procedure such that any CGM gas that cools below 3×10^4 K and has a CGM or ICM tracer less than 0.1, is relabelled to being ISM, keeping the tracer mass conserved among the two phases.

2.2 Metallicity dependent radiative cooling

We use a Cloudy (Ferland et al. 2017) generated cooling curve with solar metallicity and a γ UV background. A temperature floor at $\times 10^4$ K is assumed in all the simulations to mimic the effect of photoheating. The initial disk is assigned a metallicity of $1 Z_{\odot}$, while the initial CGM and ICM are assumed to be at $0.3 Z_{\odot}$. We follow a tracer-based metallicity evolution which is used to set the efficiency of radiative cooling in each grid cell i.e., at any instant of time, a gas cell will have a metallicity

$$f = f_{\text{ISM}}Z_{\odot} + (f_{\text{CGM}} + f_{\text{ICM}}) * 0.3 Z_{\odot}.$$

3 RESULTS

In this section, we discuss the survival of dense gas in ram pressure stripping simulations of the ISM and CGM of a galaxy, with radiative cooling. In particular, we look at the survival of cold mass in the stripped tails of our simulated jellyfish galaxy and trace its origin, by measuring the passive scalar fraction of the ISM, CGM, and ICM tracers in each grid cell.

3.1 Cold mass evolution in the disk

Figure 1 shows the distribution of dense gas in the stripped tails of our simulated galaxy with an inclination of 60 degrees between the normal to the disk plane and the wind. The leftmost panel is a zoomed region around the galactic disk showing the number density in units of cm^{-3} in a logarithmic scale. The white dense blobs of gas can be seen surviving at this time (~ 500 Myr). The other panels respectively show the passive scalars in the ISM, the CGM, and the ICM. Clearly, a non-negligible amount of CGM can be traced in the densest regions in the tail, while the ICM is still not able to interact a lot with the ISM gas.

The top panel of Figure 2 shows the evolution of the cold mass which is quantified as the mass of cells below 3×10^4 K within a cylindrical domain centered at the disk extending 30kpc in radius and 1kpc in height. Since, the shear between the CGM and rotating ISM gas produces a lot of mixing at their boundary layers, with impinging ram pressure from the wind, a fraction of CGM gas near the disk can cool below 3×10^4 K and we have relabelled such a cell if the fraction of CGM tracer has gone below a threshold value (see 2.1). This means further down the tail, we can identify the gas that was always cold when stripped from the disk, although it might have been produced by the CGM and ISM mixing near the disk.

Features of cold gas condensing out of the ICM and falling on the disk is also seen, as the gray dotted line which was initially marked as ICM, starts contributing to the cold mass in the disk beyond 600 Myr.

3.2 Cold mass evolution in the stripped tail

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the cold mass in the tail of our simulated galaxy which is quantified as the mass of cells below 3×10^4 K within a region beyond the cylindrical domain centered at the disk in the downwind direction. Since, the shear between

Figure 2. *Top panel:* Comparison of the cold mass in the disk with (solid green curve) and without (dashed green curve) cooling, as a function of time in Gyr. *Bottom panel:* A slight enhancement of cold mass in the disk due to cooling of CGM/ICM onto the disk. With the impinging ram pressure, the CGM (cyan dashed curve) is mixed with the ISM to a great extent such that gas can cool below 10^4 K. As ram pressure stripping progresses, cold gas condensed from the ICM can fall back to the disk and get mixed, which enhances the disk mass further at late times (as seen in the gray dotted curve). Following a relabelling approach described in §2.1, therefore, results in the disk mass being higher than the non-radiative simulation (as shown in the dashed green line). After an initial stripping phase (~ 200 Myr), the cold mass from the initial ISM is not stripped further.

the CGM and stripped cold ISM can produce a lot of mixing at their boundary layers, progressively increasing the mass of cold gas. After an initial burst of cold mass in the tail that is directly stripped from the ISM, a significant fraction of CGM gas can be visually seen in 1 in the stripped tails and also in 4. Initially, the origin of cold gas in the tail can, therefore, be equally attributed to the disk and the CGM. This remains the case till ~ 450 Myr as the cyan and red dashed lines remain at similar values.

Beyond ~ 600 Myr, a steep increase is seen in the contribution of ICM to the cold gas. In fact, at this time most of the CGM is lost and ICM can cool and condense in the highly disturbed wake of the ram pressure stripped galaxy continuously. The condensed gas from the ICM can fall back to the disk, as seen in the ICM contribution

Figure 3. Condensation of ICM gas in the stripped tail at late times for our fiducial run OG1e-3v800 at zero inclination between the disk normal and the wind (directed upwards). The relative fractions of various phases in the dense structures in the stripped tail. From left to right: passive scalars of ISM, CGM, and ICM on a scale of 0 to 1. At late times, the ICM contributes significantly to the cold mass (also see the surface brightness profile in Figure 5). Many clumps of cold gas can be identified to be raining down to the disk of the galaxy (cf. Figure. 4)

Figure 4. The cold (gas below 3×10^4 K) mass in the tail (region beyond the galactic disk but within the virial radius) of the jellyfish galaxy for the fiducial run OG1e-3v800 at zero inclination as a function of time in Gyr in the *solid green* curve. The contribution to the cold mass in the stripped, the CGM is mixed and cools below 10^4 K. Following a relabelling approach described in §2.1, therefore results in the disk mass being higher than the non-radiative simulation (as shown in the dashed green line)

to the disk mass in Figure 2. The fall in cold mass beyond a Gyr is due to the fact that our analysis is made only within the virial radius of the galaxy, beyond which the resolution gets worse and cold gas can be outflowing from the simulation domain.

4 DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The primary motive for this paper is to investigate the origin of the radiatively cooled gas in ram pressure striped tails.

Spectroscopic observations by MUSE (Franchetto et al. 2020) show that the metallicity in the stripped tails decreases with increasing distance from the stripped galaxy. The interpretation of this observation is that the metal-rich stripped ISM is increasingly mixed with a higher fraction of the lower-metallicity ICM and CGM over ~ 20 kpc behind the ISM wake. Figure 5 shows the surface brightness measure for our fiducial run OG1e-3v800 at ~ 700 Myr, which is calculated as the integral of $n^2\Lambda$ integrated along the x-axis. A flared wake of stripped gas shows a clumpier distribution in the emission map. The highly radiatively efficient regions have a complex contribution of ISM, CGM, and ICM mixed down the tail (see Figure 3). This is qualitatively consistent with the observational trends, although we utilize only a fixed metallicity in the disk and consider a metallicity-dependent radiative cooling (see ISM, CGM and ICM tracer panels in Figure 1). It would be interesting to obtain a similar rotation map of the tail and test if rotation inherited from the ISM can be maintained down the disk as the observations indicate signatures of decaying rotation coherence in the stripped tails (Franchetto et al. 2020; Luo et al. 2023). Further out along the tails, the ICM turbulence can dominate the line-of-sight velocity (Li et al. 2023), but we do not model a turbulent ICM in this work.

According to the classic Gunn & Gott criterion (Gunn & Gott 1972), gas from the ISM is stripped when the impinging ram pressure ($\rho_{\text{ICM}}v_{\text{rel}}^2$) exceeds the gravitational restoring pressure from the stellar and dark matter potential of the galaxy (which is $2\pi G\Sigma_*\Sigma_{\text{gas}}$ for an infinitely thin disk; $\Sigma_{*,\text{gas}}$ is the surface density of stars+dark matter, gas). With increasing ram pressure strength from $P_{\text{ram}} = 1.30 \times 10^{-13}$ dyn cm $^{-2}$ in black (PG2e-5v800) to

Figure 5. The surface brightness measure for our fiducial run, calculated as the integral of $n^2\Lambda$ integrated along the x-axis. At $\sim 700\text{Myr}$, a flared wake of stripped gas shows a clumpier distribution in the emission map. The highly radiatively efficient regions have a complex contribution of ISM, CGM, and ICM mixed down the tail (see Figure 3).

$P_{\text{ram}} = 6.49 \times 10^{-10} \text{ dyn cm}^{-2}$ in magenta, the ISM mass progressively becomes lower. The ISM mass evolution is determined solely by the ram pressure as a similar evolution. The ISM is thus ram pressure stripped as per the Gunn & Gott criterion.

However, some caveats remain in our simplistic picture of ram pressure stripping evolution. The sizes of dense clouds produced by radiative cooling can be the Jeans length and become gravitationally unstable, leading to in-situ star formation (e.g., Vulcani et al. 2018; Cramer et al. 2019). Other important physical processes that we do not model are the effects of magnetic fields, thermal conduction, and viscosity. These can lead to suppression of mixing of the clouds in the stripped tails, potentially affecting the morphology of dense cold gas (Ruszkowski et al. 2014; Tonnesen & Stone 2014; Müller et al. 2021), accounting for which is beyond the scope of our current work.

Our results are particularly interesting in explaining the existence of a truncated CGM around the Large Magellanic Cloud. Simulations by Lucchini et al. 2020 also support the CGM stripping scenario for the LMC where its circumgalactic reservoir can contribute $\approx 20\%$ to the ionized gas mass in the Magellanic stream. The stripped tail in our fiducial simulation demonstrates the co-existence of the trailing ISM and the stripped CGM down the wind (see Figures 1 & 4), thereby increasing the amount of ionized gas in the tail. However, the tidal interactions in the Large and the Small Magellanic clouds also lead to a Magellanic Bridge, which can contribute significantly to the mass budget of the atomic and ionized

phases in the Magellanic stream, which is beyond the scope of this paper.

Consideration of realistic orbits, profiles for the satellites like ESO137-001 in the Norma cluster (Sun et al. 2010; Sun et al. 2022), the LMC in our own Milky Way (Krishnarao et al. 2022), and accounting for tidal perturbations are necessary for a direct comparison with observations, an interesting avenue that we keep for future work.

Overall, we have carried out 3D hydrodynamic simulations of model galaxies with both their ISM and CGM, immersed in a constant ICM wind with radiative cooling and different metallicity in the ISM versus the CGM. We have built on our simple model (Ghosh et al. 2024) of the gas distribution of a galaxy with a rotating ISM disk and a surrounding stationary CGM. The key results from our study are summarized as follows.

(i) We have examined that varying inclinations between the disk and the wind does not affect the survival and contribution of the CGM to the cold gas, unlike the ISM stripping which depends on the inclination between the wind direction and the normal to the disk plane.

(ii) Our fiducial runs reveal that initially cold gas in jellyfish galaxy tails, like JO201, originates equally from both the ISM and the CGM. Over time, a larger fraction of cold gas forms from the condensation of ICM gas in the wake of the stripped galaxy.

(iii) Radiative cooling does not alter the CGM stripping timescale, which remains dependent on the CGM to ICM density contrast (χ). The cold mass within the ISM is notably different from the hydrodynamic runs (see Figure 2), where stronger restoring force within the stripping radius can prevent its hydrodynamic mixing, thereby sustaining the cold mass reservoir for a long time.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Data related to this work will be shared upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

REFERENCES

- Abramson A., Kenney J. D. P., 2014, *The Astronomical Journal*, 147, 63
 Bacchini C., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, 950, 24
 Bregman J. N., Anderson M. E., Miller M. J., Hodges-Kluck E., Dai X., Li J.-T., Li Y., Qu Z., 2018, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 862, 3
 Cayatte V., Kotanyi C., Balkowski C., van Gorkom J. H., 1994, *AJ*, 107, 1003
 Choi W., Kim C.-G., Chung A., 2022, *ApJ*, 936, 133
 Cramer W. J., Kenney J. D. P., Sun M., Crowl H., Yagi M., Jáchym P., Roediger E., Waldron W., 2019, *ApJ*, 870, 63
 Ferland G. J., et al., 2017, *Rev. Mex. Astron. Astrofis.*, 53, 385
 Franchetto A., et al., 2020, *ApJ*, 895, 106
 Fumagalli M., Krumholz M. R., Prochaska J. X., Gavazzi G., Boselli A., 2009, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 697, 1811

- Fumagalli M., Fossati M., Hau G. K. T., Gavazzi G., Bower R., Sun M., Boselli A., 2014, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 445, 4335
- George K., et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 519, 2426
- Ghosh R., Dutta A., Sharma P., 2024, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 531, 3445
- Gullieuszik M., et al., 2023, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 945, 54
- Gunn J. E., Gott J. Richard I., 1972, *ApJ*, 176, 1
- Jáchym P., Köppen J., Palouš J., Combes F., 2009, *A&A*, 500, 693
- Jáchym P., et al., 2019, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 883, 145
- Kenney J. D. P., Young J. S., 1989, *ApJ*, 344, 171
- Krishnarao D., et al., 2022, *Nature*, 609, 915
- Larson R. B., Tinsley B. M., Caldwell C. N., 1980, *ApJ*, 237, 692
- Lee J., Kimm T., Blaizot J., Katz H., Lee W., Sheen Y.-K., Devriendt J., Slyz A., 2022, *ApJ*, 928, 144
- Li Y., Luo R., Fossati M., Sun M., Jáchym P., 2023, *MNRAS*, 521, 4785
- Lucchini S., D’Onghia E., Fox A. J., Bustard C., Bland-Hawthorn J., Zweibel E., 2020, *Nature*, 585, 203
- Luo R., et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 521, 6266
- Mignone A., Bodo G., Massaglia S., Matsakos T., Tesileanu O., Zanni C., Ferrari A., 2007, *ApJS*, 170, 228
- Moretti A., et al., 2020, *ApJ*, 889, 9
- Moretti A., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, 955, 153
- Müller A., Iagnesi A., Poggianti B., Moretti A., Ramatsoku M., Dettmar R.-J., 2021, *Galaxies*, 9, 116
- Poggianti B. M., et al., 2016, *AJ*, 151, 78
- Poggianti B. M., et al., 2019, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 887, 155
- Roediger E., Brüggem M., 2006, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 369, 567
- Roediger E., Brüggem M., 2007, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 380, 1399
- Ruszkowski M., Brüggem M., Lee D., Shin M. S., 2014, *ApJ*, 784, 75
- Smith R. J., et al., 2010, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 408, 1417
- Sparre M., Pfrommer C., Puchwein E., 2024, *arXiv e-prints*, p. [arXiv:2405.00768](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.00768)
- Sun M., Donahue M., Roediger E., Nulsen P. E. J., Voit G. M., Sarazin C., Forman W., Jones C., 2010, *ApJ*, 708, 946
- Sun M., et al., 2022, *Nature Astronomy*, 6, 270
- Tonnesen S., Bryan G. L., 2010, *ApJ*, 709, 1203
- Tonnesen S., Bryan G. L., 2021, *ApJ*, 911, 68
- Tonnesen S., Stone J., 2014, *ApJ*, 795, 148
- Tumlinson J., Peebles M. S., Werk J. K., 2017, *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 55, 389
- Vulcani B., et al., 2018, *ApJ*, 866, L25
- Woo J., Dekel A., Faber S. M., Koo D. C., 2015, *MNRAS*, 448, 237

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